

Effect of Nitrogen Levels on Vegetative Growth of Several Varieties of Hibiscus (*Hibiscus sabdarriffa* L.)

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted in one of the fields affiliated with the Directorate of Agriculture in Diwaniyah Governorate, Abu Al-Fadl Forest Nursery during the 2023-2024 agricultural season, to study the effect of four levels of nitrogen fertilization (40, 80, 120 and 160) kg ha⁻¹, represented by the symbols F1, F2, F3, and F4, respectively, on four hibiscus cultivars (red, white, striped, and black), represented by the symbols V4, V3, V2, and V1, respectively. The experiment was conducted using a split-plot method with a Randomized Complete Block Design, with four replicates. Nitrogen fertilization levels occupied the main plots, while hibiscus cultivars occupied the sub-plots. The results showed that the nitrogen level of 160 kg ha⁻¹ was superior to other levels in plant height, number of branches, and fresh and dry weight. As for the hibiscus varieties, the V4 variety outperformed the other varieties in plant height, number of branches, and fresh and dry weight.

Keywords: *Hibiscus Sabdarriffa* L., Nitrogen fertilization, Varieties, vegetative growth.

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Introduction

Hibiscus (*Hibiscus sabdarriffa* L.) is a widely distributed plant belonging to the Malvaceae family. It is an annual or biennial shrubby plant. Its origin is in Asia and tropical regions of Africa. Some authors believe that India is the original home of the plant (Tounkara, et al., 2011). Hibiscus is an economically important crop in the central provinces of Iraq, particularly in the Al-Qadisiyah Governorate, Al-Saniyah District, where its yield reached 800 kg ha⁻¹. The medicinal importance of the plant is concentrated in the calyx leaves, which are a rich source of vitamin C, tartaric acid, and citric acid, in addition to antioxidants such as procatechins and hibiscin (Al-Sarraf, 1991; Kılıç, et al., 2011).

Anthocyanin is an antioxidant. It is one of the most important and effective plant pigments. It improves and strengthens the heart muscles, stimulates heart rhythms, and calms the nerves, reduces all types of inflammation, lowers blood sugar and high blood pressure and is an anti-cancer agent, neutralizes the harmful effects of carbon tetrachloride. Therefore, it helps eliminate liver fibrosis and reduces stomach, uterine, and intestinal cramps (Louis, et al., 2013).

Studies have shown that there are significant differences between cultivated hibiscus cultivars in plant height, number of fruits, yield, and fresh and dry calyces (Ottai, et al., 2006).

Many agricultural studies and research have shown that nitrogen is the primary nutrient that determines crop productivity. It is one of the most important and required nutrients by crops. It is also the primary determinant of a plant's ability to utilize phosphorus and potassium absorbed from the soil, due to its control over biological processes within the plant. Therefore, this study was conducted to determine the effect of nitrogen levels on the vegetative growth of several varieties of hibiscus (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.).

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site and Design

The field experiment was conducted in Diwaniyah Governorate during the summer season of 2023-2024, at Abu al-Fadl Forest Nursery, affiliated with the Diwaniyah Governorate Agriculture Directorate. The experiment was implemented using a split-plot method. A Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four replicates was used. Nitrogen fertilization levels occupied the main plots. Varieties were placed in the sub-plots. Factors were randomly distributed within each plot. Thus, the total number of experimental units was $4 \times 4 \times 4 = 64$ experimental units. The soil type in which the experiment was conducted was clayey.

Traits Studied

Plant height (cm): The height of the main stem was measured from the soil surface to the top of the growing tip using a measuring tape.

Number of branches per plant (Plant⁻¹): The number of branches was counted for five plants, and the average number of branches for each experimental unit was calculated.

Plant fresh weight (gm): The fresh weight of plants at the onset of flowering was calculated for each experimental unit and for all replicates.

Plant dry weight (gm): After taking the fresh weight of the plants at the onset of flowering, they were air-dried in a well-ventilated room away from sunlight. The drying process was completed in an electric oven at 70°C for 24-48 hours. Weights were taken at intervals until the weight stabilized using a sensitive balance.

Statistical Analysis

The experiment was analyzed according to a completely randomized block design, and significant differences between means were tested using the least significant difference (LSD) at a 5% probability level (Al-Rawi, & Khalaf Allah, 1990).

Results and Discussion

Plant Height

Table 1 shows the significant effect of nitrogen levels, cultivars, and their interaction on plant height. There were significant differences between nitrogen levels. F4 yielded the highest mean (183.30 cm), significantly superior to all other levels. It was followed by F3 and F2, with averages of 168.24 cm and 154.91 cm, respectively, while F1 recorded a significant decrease in plant height, providing the lowest average of 142.46 cm. The increase in plant height may be attributed to increased nitrogen levels. Nitrogen significantly affects vegetative growth, as well as the growth of meristematic tissues. It also contributes to the synthesis of amino acids, including tryptophan, which is the basis for the formation of indole acetic acid (IAA), which is important and essential for cell division and cell elongation, allows for

increased plant height (Devlin, & Witham, 2000; Mengel, & Kirkby, 2004). These results were consistent with Al-Hassan and Al-Awadi (2011); Al-Dabbin (2022).

The results showed that cultivar V4 recorded the highest average plant height of 204.62 cm, significantly outperforming the other averages. This was followed by cultivars V1 and V2, with averages of 169.71 and 142.67 cm, respectively, with a significant difference between them. cultivar V3 recorded a significant decrease compared to the other cultivars, with an average of 132.90 cm. This may be due to the genetic and environmental interaction during the study period, which affects growth, this interaction is significantly reflected in plant height, particularly climatic variations, especially temperature. These results were consistent with Bizuayehu and Basazine (2016); Wachamo *et al.* (2022); Al-Jumaili (2023).

As for the interaction between nitrogen levels and cultivars, it had a significant effect. The combination (F4×V4) yielded the highest average (228.65 cm), while the combination (F1×V3) yielded the lowest average (110.85 cm).

Table 1. The Effect of Nitrogen Levels, Varieties, and the Interaction between Them on the Plant Height Trait (cm)

Nitrogen levels	Varieties				Mean
	V1	V2	V3	V4	
F1	151.15	123.50	110.85	184.32	142.46
F2	163.10	133.30	126.85	196.40	154.91
F3	176.60	150.75	136.50	209.10	168.24
F4	188.00	159.15	157.40	228.65	183.30
Mean	169.71	141.67	132.90	204.62	
L.S.D _{0.05}	F		V		F×V
	1.937		1.937		3.873

Number of Branches per Plant (plant⁻¹):

Table 2 shows a significant effect of nitrogen levels, cultivars, and their interaction on the number of branches per plant. F4, recorded a significant superiority in the number of branches per plant, with an average of 68.69 branches per plant. This was followed by F3, and F2, with averages of 55.60 and 44.05 branches per plant, respectively, While F1 level recorded the lowest average, at 36.55 branches. Plant. The reason for the superiority of the F4 level may be due to the fact that nitrogen significantly influences the increase in vegetative growth in plants. It also influences the formation of cytokinins, which play a significant role in the growth of buds and branches (Mengel, & Kirkby, 2004; Nasrallah, 2012). This result is consistent with Al-Hassan and Al-Awadi (2011); Al-Dabbin (2022); Al-Badiri (2001); Al-Halfi *et al.* (2017).

The results showed that hibiscus cultivars achieved a significant increase in the number of branches per plant, compared to cultivar V3, which had the lowest average of 30.56 branches per plant, while cultivar V4 significantly outperformed the other cultivars, yielding the highest average of 74.70 branches per plant. This was followed by cultivars V1 and V2, with averages of 61.46 and 38.16 branches per plant, respectively. This increase may be due to differences in genetic factors between cultivars, as well as environmental factors and their suitability for the cultivar. This is consistent with Al-Hadwani (2004), who noted genetic differences between fenugreek cultivars, and Al-Taie (2017) in his study of several hibiscus cultivars.

Regarding the interaction between nitrogen levels and cultivars, the results indicated a significant effect on the average number of branches per plant. The combination (F4×V4) achieved the highest average

number of branches per plant, reaching 93.40, while the combination (F1×V3) produced the lowest average number of branches, reaching 19.65 branches per plant.

Table 2. Effect of Nitrogen Levels, Cultivars, and Their Interaction on the Number of Branches per Plant

Nitrogen levels	Varieties				Mean
	V1	V2	V3	V4	
F1	42.05	27.45	19.65	57.05	36.55
F2	51.05	32.20	24.55	68.40	44.05
F3	68.55	40.35	33.55	79.95	55.60
F4	84.20	52.65	44.50	93.40	68.69
Mean	61.64	38.16	30.56	74.70	
L.S.D _{0.05}	F		V		F×V
	1.662		1.662		3.324

Fresh Weight of the Vegetative Mass (gm plant)

Table 3 indicates a significant effect of nitrogen levels, cultivars, and their interaction on the fresh weight of the plant's vegetative mass. The results showed that nitrogen levels significantly affected the average fresh weight of the vegetative mass of a plant. F4 level yielded the highest average of 2002.3 gm, significantly superior to the other levels, while F1 level yielded the lowest average of 1251.4 gm. The reason for the increase in fresh weight of the vegetative mass may be due to the increased nitrogen level. Nitrogen availability leads to the formation of tender plants with a high content of protoplasmic substances filled with water. This result is consistent with Al-Bou Khedher (2019), the increase in fresh weight of the vegetative mass of sweet cumin plants is due to increased nitrogen.

The results also indicated that hibiscus cultivars significantly affected the fresh weight of the plant's shoots. Cultivar V4 achieved the highest average fresh weight of the shoots, reaching 2276.5 gm. Cultivars V1 and V2 followed, with averages of 1714.2 and 1209.5. Cultivar V3, meanwhile, had the lowest average fresh weight, reaching 1121.9 gm. This is likely due to the influence of the cultivar's genotype. The increased growth of the Black cultivar may be due to the environmental conditions of the study area.

The interaction between nitrogen levels and cultivars had a significant effect on the fresh weight of the plant's vegetative mass. The combination (F4×V4) yielded the highest average fresh weight of the vegetative mass, reaching 2888.6 gm plant, a significant difference from the other combinations, while the combination (F1×V3) yielded the lowest average for the trait, reaching 1005.4 gm plant.

Table 3. Effect of Nitrogen Levels, Cultivars, and Their Interaction on the Fresh Weight of the Vegetative Mass

Nitrogen levels	Varieties				Mean
	V1	V2	V3	V4	
F1	1200.7	1134.8	1005.4	1664.8	1251.4
F2	1334.9	1184.0	1128.3	2183.1	1457.6
F3	1711.5	1205.3	1156.7	2369.7	1610.8
F4	2609.6	1313.9	1197.0	2888.6	2002.3
Mean	1714.5	1209.5	1121.9	2276.5	
L.S.D _{0.05}	F		V		F×V
	9.210		9.210		18.420

Dry Weight of the Vegetative Mass

Table 4 shows the significant effect of nitrogen levels, hibiscus cultivars, and their interaction on plant dry weight. The results indicate significant differences between nitrogen levels in the dry weight of the vegetative mass. The F4 level yielded the highest average of 588.15 gm, significantly superior to the other levels, it was followed by F3 and F2 levels, with averages of 477.93 and 364.54 gm, respectively, significantly superior to F1 level, which yielded the lowest average of 313.08. The reason for the superiority of the F4 level is that it provides the highest average. Nitrogen is a component of the chlorophyll molecule, which encourages good vegetative growth. This leads to the accumulation of photosynthetic products and, consequently, an increase in the dry weight of the plant. Nitrogen is a component of the bases for amino acids, purines, and pyrimidines. This result is consistent with Al-Badiri (2001); Al-Halfi *et al.* (2017); Al-Asadi (2006), when they used different levels of nitrogen on hibiscus plants. Al-Bou Khader (2019), studied the sweet seed plant, and Al-Dabbin (2022), studied the hibiscus plant.

Table 4. The Effect of Nitrogen Levels, Varieties, and the Interaction between Them on the Dry Weight of the Vegetative Mass

Nitrogen levels	Varieties				Mean
	V1	V2	V3	V4	
F1	301.95	275.25	244.05	431.05	313.08
F2	340.10	299.00	272.70	546.35	364.54
F3	440.55	369.20	339.25	762.70	477.93
F4	538.20	426.10	408.00	980.30	588.15
Mean	405.20	342.39	316.00	680.10	
L.S.D _{0.05}	F		V		F×V
	3.304		3.304		6.608

Conclusion

The results also indicated that cultivars significantly affected plant dry weight. Cultivar V4 achieved the highest average dry weight of the vegetative mass, reaching 680.10 gm, followed by cultivar V1, with an average of 405.20 gm, while cultivars V2 and V3 recorded the lowest averages, reaching 342.39 and 316.00 gm, respectively. This may be due to the influence of the cultivar's genotype, or the increased vegetative growth of the Black cultivar and its superior plant height and number of branches, which led to an increase in plant dry weight. This result is consistent with Al-Hassan and Al-Awadi (2011); Al Salman and Al-Gharawi (2019), who indicated that hibiscus cultivars differed significantly in vegetative growth characteristics, including plant dry weight.

As for the interaction between the two factors, the results of the statistical analysis showed that the combination (F4×V4) was significantly superior to the other combinations, with an average of 980.30 gm. While the combination (F1×V3) had the lowest average of 244.5 gm.

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